

PREVALENCE OF HEART FAILURE WITH PRESERVED EJECTION FRACTION IN A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL OF KARACHI

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Abstract

Background: Heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF) has become a prevalent and clinically unique subtype of heart failure. However, there is a lack of comprehensive data regarding its prevalence and the risk factors associated with HFpEF in South Asian populations.

Study Design: Cross-Sectional Study.

Study Setting: The study conducted at the Indus Hospital and Health Network, Karachi

Study Duration: four Months (March to June 2025)

Methodology: We enrolled 175 adult patients with a clinical diagnosis of heart failure. Demographic information, clinical history, and echocardiographic data was gathered from the participants to identify HFpEF cases. We used chi-square tests to assess associations between HFpEF and patient characteristics, including comorbidities and smoking status.

Results: HFpEF was present in 36% of the study population. Patients with HFpEF were more likely to report a history of smoking ($p = 0.01$) and a family history of premature coronary artery disease ($p = 0.02$). We observed lower HFpEF prevalence among patients with dyslipidemia ($p = 0.01$), ischemic heart disease ($p = 0.01$), and atrial fibrillation ($p = 0.01$). Age, gender, diabetes, and BMI did not show statistically significant associations with HFpEF.

Conclusion: In this hospital-based data set, we found a substantial burden of HFpEF, particularly among patients without overt atherosclerotic disease but with identifiable lifestyle and familial risk factors. These results emphasize the need for screening approaches tailored to specific contexts and underscore the necessity of early risk detection, particularly in settings with limited resources.

INTRODUCTION

Heart failure (HF) is defined by structural and/or functional abnormalities of the heart that compromise its ability to pump blood effectively, resulting in a complex clinical syndrome marked by characteristic signs and symptoms. It is broadly categorized into heart failure with reduced ejection

fraction (HFrEF) and heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF) based on left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF). HFpEF is defined as HF with LVEF $> 50\%$.¹ The 2021 European Society of Cardiology guidelines give a strong (Class I) recommendation emphasizing the evaluation and

management of underlying causes and both cardiovascular and non-cardiovascular comorbidities, highlighting the critical role these factors play in HFpEF.² Among hypertensive patients, HFpEF presents a complex clinical entity with diagnostic complexities and limited therapeutic avenues.^{3,5} Data from the Framingham Heart Study showed a rising share of heart failure cases classified as HFpEF (left ventricular ejection fraction $\geq 50\%$), increasing from 41% during 1985–1994 to 56% in 2005–2014.⁶ Studies have reported a substantial prevalence of atrial fibrillation (AF) in patients with HFpEF, ranging between 15% and 40%, depending on the specific cohort and the methods used to detect AF. Notably, AF acts not only as a common comorbidity in HFpEF but also as a bidirectional risk factor, influencing the development and progression of the condition.⁷ The PREVEND study demonstrated a strong association between older age and new-onset HFpEF (HR 2.53; 95% CI [1.93–3.30], per 10 years).⁸ Even though there are currently no therapies that alter the course of HFpEF, examining the phenotypic patterns and variations among HFpEF patients worldwide is essential for facilitating early diagnosis, guiding management, and identifying modifiable risk factors for preventive strategies. Regardless of its increasing recognition, data on HFpEF prevalence in specific populations, such as ours, remains limited, specifically in our region, where almost no direct prevalence studies have been done.⁹

This study aims to describe the clinical and echocardiographic profile of patients with Heart Failure with preserved Ejection Fraction (Hfpef) and identify associated risk factors. Understanding these factors will help identify at-risk patients and guide targeted management. Knowing the prevalence of Hfpef in Pakistan will inform healthcare resource allocation and management strategies

METHODOLOGY:

This study followed a cross-sectional design and was conducted at the outpatient clinics of the Indus Hospital and Health Network in Karachi. A sample size of 175 participants has been determined using OpenEpi software, based on a

95% confidence interval and an expected prevalence of heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF) in hypertensive patients to be 53.9%. Participants were recruited through non-probability consecutive sampling.

Hypertensive adults aged 18–80 who were using at least one antihypertensive medication were eligible. The study requires informed written and verbal agreement from all participants. Systolic heart failure (HF_rEF or HF_mrEF), non-hypertension, inability or unwillingness to give informed consent, severe comorbid conditions like end-stage renal disease or malignancies that could affect study outcomes, or enrolment in another clinical trial that may interfere with participation were excluded. The AHA defines heart failure with intact ejection fraction as symptomatic or asymptomatic HF with LVEF $\geq 50\%$.

Data was acquired by the researcher after informed consent. Demographic data included age, gender, BMI (weight in kilogrammes divided by height in meters), and comorbidities including diabetes and dyslipidaemia. Participants' functional level, smoking history, and positive family history of cardiovascular diseases (including ischaemic heart disease, heart failure, or sudden cardiac death among first-degree relatives) were recorded during the interview. Each participant was referred for echocardiographic evaluation as part of standard baseline cardiac assessment, and HFpEF was diagnosed based on echocardiographic criteria needing at least three of four findings.

Scatter plots and the Shapiro-Wilk test determined normality for continuous variables including age, height, weight, and BMI. If data was regularly distributed, means with standard deviations were reported; otherwise, medians and interquartile ranges. Sex, BMI categories, atrial fibrillation history, diabetes, and HFpEF status (yes/no) were summarised using frequencies and percentages. Variables were stratified to determine their effect on primary outcomes. Post-stratification analysis used chi-square or Fisher's exact tests, with a p-value ≤ 0.05 indicating statistical significance.

RESULTS:

This study included 175 patients. Most participants (68.6%) were aged between 55–80 years. The

remaining 31.4% were aged 18–55 years. The sample was slightly more female (53.1%) than male (46.9%). Diabetes was reported by 29.1% of subjects. Nearly half (46.9%) had dyslipidaemia, and 24% had ischaemic heart disease. Atrial fibrillation was found in 16% of data. Smoking was present in 36.6%. A family history of early coronary artery disease was reported by 20% of individuals. We found that 60% of patients had BMI levels above 30 kg/m².

We diagnosed Heart Failure with Preserved Ejection Fraction (HFpEF) in 36% of the dataset, while 64% did not meet HFpEF criteria. Table 2 compares patient characteristics between individuals with and without HFpEF. We did not observe statistically significant differences in HFpEF prevalence across

age groups (p = 0.78), gender (p = 0.64), diabetes status (p = 0.24), or BMI categories (p = 0.36). However, multiple factors greatly affected HFpEF. Patients without dyslipidaemia had more HFpEF (p = 0.01). Without ischaemic heart disease (p = 0.01) or atrial fibrillation (p = 0.01), HFpEF was more common. Smoking history also positively correlated with HFpEF (p = 0.01). Patients with a family history of early CAD had greater incidences of HFpEF (p = 0.02).

Patients without atherosclerotic disease but with lifestyle and familial risk factors had higher rates of HFpEF. Smoking and a family history of early CAD may cause persistent inflammation and vascular dysfunction in HFpEF, suggesting a non-ischemic route.

Table 1: Baseline characteristics and their association with Heart Failure with Preserved Ejection Fraction (HFpEF) among study participants (n = 175)

Variables	Total n (%)	HFpEF Present n (%)	HFpEF Absent n (%)	p-value
Age (years)				
18–55	55 (31.4)	19 (34.5)	36 (65.5)	0.78
56–80	120 (68.6)	44 (36.7)	76 (63.3)	
Gender				
Male	82 (46.9)	31 (37.8)	51 (62.2)	0.64
Female	93 (53.1)	32 (34.4)	61 (65.6)	
Diabetes Mellitus	51 (29.1)	15 (29.4)	36 (70.6)	0.24
Dyslipidemia	82 (46.9)	13 (15.9)	69 (84.1)	0.01
Ischemic Heart Disease	42 (24.0)	7 (16.7)	35 (83.3)	0.01
Atrial Fibrillation	28 (16.0)	1 (3.6)	27 (96.4)	0.01
Smoking Status	64 (36.6)	31 (48.4)	33 (51.6)	0.01
Family History of Premature CAD	35 (20.0)	7 (20.0)	28 (80.0)	0.02
BMI Status				
≤30 kg/m ²	70 (40.0)	28 (40.0)	42 (60.0)	0.36
>30 kg/m ²	105 (60.0)	35 (33.3)	70 (66.7)	
Overall HFpEF Prevalence	63 (36.0)	–	–	–

Figure 1: Percentage distribution of HFpEF prevalence across key clinical and lifestyle subgroups.

DISCUSSION:

In this study, we observed that 36% of patients presenting with heart failure at a tertiary care center in Karachi met the criteria for Heart Failure with Preserved Ejection Fraction (HFpEF). A majority of the study population was aged 55 to 80 years. The age distribution matches comparable community-based and hospital registries globally.¹¹⁻¹² Although HFpEF is often described as a condition predominantly affecting women, our findings revealed only a modest female predominance. This could reflect population-specific factors, including healthcare-seeking behavior and referral patterns, which warrant further investigation.¹³

Notably, patients with HFpEF were significantly less prone to have dyslipidemia, ischemic heart disease, or atrial fibrillation. These associations diverge from findings in landmark trials, where patients with HFpEF frequently had multiple cardiovascular comorbidities.¹⁴ In our setting, reduced detection of ischemic heart disease and arrhythmias might result from limitations in access to advanced diagnostic tools like coronary angiography and Holter monitoring. Furthermore, the inverse relationship between atrial fibrillation and HFpEF observed in our study contrasts with data from other studies, which reported atrial

fibrillation as a strong predictor of incident HFpEF.¹⁵

Our results also indicate a significant association between HFpEF and both smoking and a family history of premature coronary artery disease. Although smoking is well established as a modifiable risk factor for cardiovascular disease. Its role in the pathogenesis of HFpEF has been inconsistently documented.¹⁶ Some researchers have suggested that chronic exposure to tobacco accelerates microvascular dysfunction and systemic inflammation, which may contribute to myocardial stiffening in the absence of overt ischemia.¹⁷ The familial clustering of HFpEF in our data set reinforces findings from the Framingham Heart Study, where parental history of cardiovascular disease was associated with increased heart failure risk in offspring.⁶

Interestingly, our analysis did not find a significant association between diabetes mellitus and HFpEF. This result contrasts with multiple Western studies, which have consistently shown diabetes to be a robust predictor of HFpEF development.

These differences may stem from regional disparities in glycemic control, treatment adherence, or diagnostic sensitivity. Obesity has been extensively linked to HFpEF due to its contribution to increased ventricular stiffness and systemic inflammation.

However, we did not observe a statistically significant difference in HFpEF prevalence between BMI categories. This may reflect the limitations of BMI as a surrogate for visceral adiposity. This is particularly so among South Asian populations, where lower thresholds may better capture metabolic risk.¹⁸⁻¹⁹

The heterogeneity of clinical profiles among patients with HFpEF aligns with emerging views that HFpEF represents a syndrome with diverse pathophysiological mechanisms rather than a single disease entity. Researchers have increasingly advocated for phenotypic clustering to improve trial design and therapeutic targeting. In our population, the clustering of HFpEF with non-atherosclerotic risk factors: such as family history and smoking, suggests a potentially distinct phenotype that may benefit from tailored screening strategies.^{20,21}

Our findings are comparable to local evidence who studied HFpEF in a similar tertiary setting and reported comparable demographic patterns. These researchers noted a higher burden of ischemic heart disease and procedural history among HFrEF patients. Taken together, these results underscore the need for region-specific epidemiological data to inform guidelines, particularly in low- and middle-income countries where diagnostic infrastructure and treatment pathways differ from those in high-income settings.

CONCLUSION:

We found that HFpEF affected more than one-third of patients presenting with heart failure in our tertiary care setting. Patients with HFpEF were more likely to report a history of smoking and a family history of premature CAD, and less likely to have ischemic heart disease or atrial fibrillation. These patterns suggest that HFpEF in this population may follow a distinct clinical profile, shaped more by lifestyle and familial factors than by traditional atherosclerotic disease. Our findings point to the need for improved risk assessment strategies and context-specific approaches to early identification and management of HFpEF.

LIMITATIONS

We conducted a cross-sectional analysis, which prevented us from assessing temporal or causal relationships between risk factors and HFpEF. We also did not include detailed echocardiographic

measures of diastolic function, which may have limited the diagnostic accuracy for HFpEF classification.

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